

R.T.Pardayev, B.Yuldasheva

Teacher, Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Abstract. The creative process in urban planning is based on careful preservation of past examples, cultural and architectural monuments, but at the same time rejects blind imitation, because the developing society constantly changes its material, aesthetic forms and ideals. People's self-awareness and cultural change, the development of construction techniques, the appearance of new building materials, which led to a high level of development of architecture. Therefore, all the design and construction process carried out in the urban development is necessarily carried out on the basis of conditions and factors representing national traditions. This article examines the principles of development of the tasks set in urban planning based on national historical traditions.

Key words. Urban planning, socio-economic factor, urbanization, demography, settlements.

НАЦИОНАЛЬНО-ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ТРАДИЦИИ В ГОРОДЕ

Р.Т.Пардаев, Б.Юлдашева

Преподаватель, Самаркандский государственный университет
архитектуры и строительства,
Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Аннотация. Творческий процесс в градостроительстве основан на бережном сохранении образцов прошлого, памятников культуры и архитектуры, но в то же время отвергает слепое подражание, поскольку развивающееся общество постоянно меняет свои материальные, эстетические формы и идеалы. Самосознание народа и культурные изменения, развитие строительных технологий, появление новых строительных материалов привели к высокому уровню развития архитектуры. Поэтому весь процесс проектирования и строительства, осуществляемый в сфере городского развития, обязательно осуществляется с учетом условий и факторов,

отражающих национальные традиции. В данной статье рассматриваются принципы разработки задач, поставленных в градостроительстве, исходя из национальных исторических традиций.

Ключевые слова. Городское планирование, социально-экономические факторы, урбанизация, демография, поселения.

Introduction. Urban planning is the theory and practice of planning and construction of cities and settlements, which comprehensively solves socio-economic, sanitary-hygiene, technical transport construction and architectural-artistic tasks related to design and construction. Residential system, taking into account socio-economic tasks, as well as national traditions, prospects for the development of cities or settlements, economically efficient use of natural and territorial resources, reasonable population growth and optimal organization of cultural and household services for the population are the factors to be decided in the selection.

The development of national culture is determined by the progressive characteristics and traditions of the international formation of a certain region or continent, where the natural and climatic characteristics of the geographical environment are the basis for the formation of national traditions.

Social way of life and social relations have a significant influence on the formation of specific characteristics of national traditions. For example, based on ancient traditions, Russian classicism of the 18th century became a unique phenomenon of Russian culture.

Methodhs. The process of designing on the basis of national traditions is evident in developing countries that have gone to the path of strengthening national identity. Together with the struggle for political independence and independence, a complex process of strengthening national culture takes place here. At the same time, the process of internationalization and rapprochement of cultures of different peoples, united by common humanistic principles of urban planning and architecture, takes place here. During this period, strong efforts to liberate the peoples of the colonial countries and to strengthen the national identity of the developing countries created a unique national culture. Advanced national schools of architecture have emerged in India, Africa, Latin America and other regions of the world. The formation of these schools is related to social, economic and natural-climatic events in the general

development of progressive urban development. As a result, Brazil, Chandigarh, Skopje and other large cities appeared.

The main terms representing national traditions in urban planning include:

- specific natural-climatic factors that operate historically for a long time, in particular, characteristic of a warm climate, as well as geographical environment;
- the influence of a specific socio-economic situation in which national traditions are formed;
- level of technological development of society.

Results. In the process of development of national traditions, the demographic composition, as well as the artistic and aesthetic ideals of the people, which include the uniqueness of tastes, ideas and criteria in building aesthetics, play an important role. The experience and practice of world construction in certain natural and climatic conditions leads to the development of a single architectural and urban planning technique, in which the national tradition turns into international traditions.

Thus, verandas emerged as a result of centuries of experience in dealing with the thermal factor that has a negative effect on the human body. A shaded courtyard surrounded by a gallery on all sides creates a deep shade that cools the walls and the houses behind them. The water fountain in the center of the courtyard and the green areas gradually provide coolness and moisture to the space surrounding the courtyard during the hot day. The popular experience of house planning was also used in the construction of a large public ensemble, such as Registan, with a madrasah located around large enclosed courtyards with a favorable microclimate. It seems that in hot dry climates, the time-tested historically derived closed composite method can be widely used in modern urban planning practice.

The development of the national economy, the specific lifestyle of people, as well as the development of the landscape have a significant impact on the formation of the national identity of urban planning and architecture. The level of construction techniques and the uniqueness of local building materials play an important role in determining the characteristics of national traditions.

The creative process in urban planning is based on careful preservation of past examples, cultural and architectural monuments, but at the same time rejects blind imitation, because the developing society constantly changes its material, aesthetic forms and ideals. People's self-awareness and cultural change, the development of

construction techniques, the appearance of new building materials, which led to a high level of development of architecture.

Therefore, the change of structure and further development of historical cities should probably be related to the problem of comprehensive preservation of the entire historical and architectural heritage system, and not individual architectural monuments, because the basis of the historical city structure the laws of its formation over time, such laws include:

- general characteristics of microclimate;
- main compositional axes and their direction to the countries of the world;
- direction of prevailing winds;
- spatial connections between individual monuments;
- panoramic perception zones;
- historical environment;
- landscape of the area;
- impact of existing public development etc. (background development).

In short, the wooden architecture of the North, the white stone walls of ancient Moscow, different shades of Armenian tuff, the modern housing construction of Eastern cities, etc. are characteristic only for a certain region.

Conclusions. Over the centuries, national technology has historically developed, and traditions determined by climatic conditions - construction site, building materials, and people's aesthetic requirements - have been developed. And finally, the daily lifestyle and psycho-physiological characteristics of the national character, which have developed over thousands of years, determined the purposeful organization of life and life.

However, under the influence of new historical conditions, the aesthetic ideals of the people can change, reject the outdated traditions and retain only the characteristics that meet the new requirements of life, new political and social factors.

Literature.

1. Rimsha A.N. Gradostroitelstvo v usloviyax jarkogo klimata. Moscow Stroyzdat 1979.

2. Lavrov V.A. Gradostroitelnaya kultura Sredney Asia (from early times to the second half of the XIX century). Gosudarstvennoe izdatelstvo po arkhitektury i gradostroitelstva. Moscow, 1950. — 179 p.

3. Fozilova, Z. Q. (2023). Irrigation System of Samarkand City. *Journal of engineering, mechanics and modern architecture*, 2(2), 64-68.

4 Fozilova, Z. Q. (2023). Samarqand shahrining bosh rejalari tahlili. *Arxitektura, muhandislik va zamonaviy texnologiyalar jurnali*, 2(1), 117-122.

5. Салохиддинова, Д. З., Каюмов, Х. И., & Фозилова, З. К. (2023). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЗАСТРОЙКИ ГОРОДА САМАРКАНДА И ЕЕ РЕШЕНИЯ. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 300-305.

6. Салохиддинова, Д. З., & Каюмов, Х. И. (2012). Мавзолей Саманидов в загадках и легендах: инженерные приёмы шедевра архитектуры Узбекистана. In *Материалы международной конференции “Современная архитектура и инновации”*.

7. Фозилова, З. Қ., & Каюмов, Х. И. (2023). САМАРКАНД-ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОХРАНЕНИЯ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЙ ГОРОДСКОЙ СРЕДЫ. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 249-253.

8. Fozilova, Z. Q. (2023). Samarqand shahrining bosh rejalari tahlili. *Arxitektura, muhandislik va zamonaviy texnologiyalar jurnali*, 2(1), 117-122.

9. Fozilova, Z. Q., & Xamroqulov, O. (2023). SHAHARSOZLIKDAGI MILLIY-TARIXIY AN'ANALAR. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 245-248.

10. Fozilova, Z. Q., Xamroqulov, O., & Yorqulov, F. I. (2023). O'ZBEKISTONDA EKOTURIZM MARSHRUTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN*, 258-262.

11. Salokhiddinova, D. Z., Kayumov, H. I., & Fozilova, Z. K. (2023). Problems of development of the city of Samarkand and its solutions. *central asian journal of arts and design*, 333-338.

12. Kayumov, H. I., & Fazilova, Z. K. (2023). Organization of traffic flow and optimization of underground-overground passages. the importance of studying optimization of the road transport network in the training of architects–urban planners. *journal of engineering, mechanics and modern architecture*, 477-482.

13. Rakhmanova, M. B. (2023). TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURAL FORMS IN MODERN BUILDINGS IN UZBEKISTAN. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, (2), 241-244.

14. Xayitboyev, N. K., & Pardayev, R. T. (2023). O'zbekistonda an'anaviy turar-joy binolarining shakllanish bosqichlari. *Central asian journal of arts and design*, 254-257.
15. Dostonov, A. S., & Xayitboyev, N. K. (2024). SHAHARSOZLIK EKOLOGIYASI MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY YECHIMLARIDA "AQLI SHAHAR" LARNING ORNI. *Interpretation and researches*.
16. Pardayev, R. T., & Khayitboyev, N. K. (2023). Principles of formation of domes of architectural monuments of the city of samarkand. *Central asian journal of arts and design*,
17. Fozilova, Z. Q., & Khayitboyev, N. K. (2024). THE ROLE OF "SMART CITIES" IN THE PROBLEMS OF URBAN ECOLOGY AND THEIR MODERN SOLUTIONS. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 3(8), 95-103.
18. Dostonov, A. S., & Fozilova, Z. Q. (2024). O'ZBEKISTONDA AN'ANAVIY TURAR-JOY BINOLARINING SHAKLLANISH BOSQICHLARI. *Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology (2995-486X)*, 251-253.
19. Каюмов, Х. И., & Фозилова, З. К. (2024). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПЕРЕБРОСА ЧАСТИ ВОД СИБИРСКИХ РЕК В ОБРАЛО КАСПИЙСКУЮ ВОДНУЮ СИСТЕМУ. *Interpretation and researches*.
20. Abdirasulovna, M. N. (2023). Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 398-400.
21. Исламова, Д. Г., & Масаридинова, Н. (2021). КОНЦЕПЦИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL*, 317.
22. Salomovich, T. E., Samariddinovich, S. U., & Pulatovich, M. B. (2023). Improving the Heat Preservation Properties of the Exterior Walls of Brick Buildings. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 28, 15-20.
23. Turakulovna, E. M. U., & Pulatovich, M. B. (2024). Characteristics of Materials that Increase the Heat Resistance of Walls. *Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology (2995-486X)*, 2(2), 36-39.